

THE TASKS OF PROSECUTORIAL CONTROL OVER THE IMPLEMENTATION OF LAWS IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF PATRIOTISM.

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Annotation. The object of the study is the activity of the Prosecutor's office to monitor the implementation of laws in the field of education of youth in the spirit of patriotism and other regulatory legal documents regulating this activity. The object of the study is the legal relations arising in the process of organizing and living of young people.

Implementation of prosecutorial control over the implementation of laws in the field of education in the spirit of patriotism. The purpose of the work is to develop theoretical rules and develop legislative, organizational and methodological proposals aimed at improving efficiency. The activities of the Prosecutor's Office to monitor the implementation of laws in the field of education of youth in the spirit of patriotism.

Keywords: prosecutorial supervision, patriotic education, patriotic education system, tasks of prosecutorial supervision, military service, education, patriotic education program, youth policy.

According to the explanatory dictionary of the modern Uzbek language ¹, "task" is a question that needs to be solved, a solution, something that is asked to be solved. At the same time, it is a task and a duty that must be implemented, solved, intended goal, purposeful work, always implemented, followed, performed. Therefore, it is impossible to distinguish between the meaning of the mission and the goal. Describing the role of the prosecutor's office in general, as AX Kazarina noted, the prosecutor's office has always solved important problems of state building ².

Elaborating on this idea, VP Ryabtsev ³says that at each historical stage the tasks of the prosecutor's supervision are dynamic and aimed at the implementation of the political direction set by the country's leadership. In his opinion, the prosecutor's office, which is part of the system of presidential power, solves the problems of effective organization of the system of mutual restraint and balance established in the state.

OP Kopylova, ⁴tasks are distinguished from goals by their more specific nature. Solving problems will help you achieve your goal.

¹https://n.ziyouz.com/books/uzbek_tiling_izohli_lugati/Uzbek%20tiling%20izohli%20lug%20ati%20-%20V.pdf

²Kazarina AX Selected works / comp. RV Jubrin, Yu.V. Vajina, VA Nemirovsky; enters. Art. FM Kobzareva; Academic Gen. Prosecutor's Office of the Russian Federation. (Scientific works of scientists of the Academy of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Russian Federation) [Text] / M.-2014. - page 44.

³Ryabtsev VP Selected works / comp. RV Jubrin, Yu.V. Vajina, VA Nemirovsky; enters. Art. FM Kobzareva; Academic Gen. Prosecutor's Office of the Russian Federation (scientific works of scientists of the Academy of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Russian Federation) [Text] M.-2014. - B. 12-13.

⁴Kopylova OP Prosecutor's supervision: training manual [Text] / Tambov: Tamb publishing house. state _ technology . University, 2007. - B. 9.

It is known that one of the main tasks of the prosecutor's office is to ensure the rule of law. In my opinion, I would like to divide the tasks of the prosecutor's supervision into three groups: 1) the tasks of ensuring a unified legal space; 2) tasks of combating crime; 3) organizational tasks.

The first group includes such tasks as ensuring the exact and uniform fulfillment of the requirements of the current legislation; harmonization of issued regulatory legal documents with the Constitution and laws; Ensuring the observance of the rights and freedoms of people and citizens in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan; Protection of the interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan through court proceedings.

The second group of tasks is related to ensuring the implementation of the principle of responsibility for committed offenses and crimes. Thus, in my opinion, this block of tasks includes the tasks of coordination of law enforcement agencies in the fight against crime, the detection of crimes, the prosecution of criminals, the prevention of crimes and the legality of the execution of punishments.

We can include information, analytical tasks, international cooperation tasks, personnel training tasks in the third group of organizational tasks.

All these three groups of tasks are dealt with in each area of the prosecutor's supervision, including the prosecutor's supervision over the execution of laws.

The main tasks of the prosecutor's office are the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, The Law "On the Prosecutor's Office" and other legislative documents are described in the orders of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of organizing prosecutorial control over the implementation of laws, observance of human and citizen's rights and freedoms.

Most researchers in the category of tasks of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of laws divide them into general, special and private.

General tasks are specific to all areas of the prosecutor's office, special tasks are specific to each area, and personal or tactical tasks are temporary in nature.

The main task of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of laws in the field of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism is to reduce the number of crimes and offenses against the interests of the Motherland.

As another task of the prosecutor's supervision, we can include tasks of the prosecutor's supervision in the field of implementation of laws on educating young people in the spirit of patriotism.

As mentioned above, tasks of the prosecutor's supervision can be divided into general (inter-branch) and special (branch) tasks, taking into account the scope of the prosecutor's supervision.

It applies to the general tasks of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of laws in the field of educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, and we will consider these tasks below.

Organization of legal monitoring of compliance with the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and current legal documents of the regulatory legal documents of state authorities, local state authorities, taking response measures by the prosecutor in case of violations of the law; elimination of deficiencies in legal regulations in the field of patriotic education.

The monitoring of the practice of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of laws on patriotic education allows us to conclude that one of the common violations is the lack of legal regulation of this area at the city and regional levels. Thus, often state authorities and local authorities do not adopt appropriate programs of patriotic education.

At the same time, ⁵taking into account Article 15 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On General Military Obligation and Military Service" and the provisions of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Local State Power" , such programs ⁶must be implemented.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan contains an important sign that the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan carries out a unified state policy. It should be concluded from the constitutional norm specified in Article 115 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan that uniform approaches should be used in the implementation of state policy in the field of education.

Thus, according to Article 50 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the absolute authority of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes the approval of republican educational standards, including educational programs and requirements for socialization of students.

Today, the state body authorized to approve educational standards is the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The peculiarity of the legislation on patriotic education is that, since these issues are of special state importance, most of them fall under the exclusive competence of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

In particular, in order to solve issues of local importance, such as organization and implementation of activities for working with children and youth, local state authorities are empowered.

As part of the implementation of the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 09.10.2019 No. PF-5847 "On approval of the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period until 2030 developed a strategy for the development of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan ⁷.

It also envisages the formation of patriotism based on special programs of military-patriotic education, the development of respect for the state symbols, historical symbols and monuments of the Republic of Uzbekistan among the young generation (not specified in the strategy, as they are defined in the relevant laws of the republic), search activities. development and others.

These instructions should be reflected and implemented within the republican programs of patriotic education in accordance with the provisions of the decisions of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which approved the relevant 10-year programs of patriotic education in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The lack of patriotic education programs in the regions leads to unsystematic work in the field of patriotic education and causes low effectiveness of these activities.

⁵Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated 12.12.2002 No. 436-II, <https://lex.uz/docs/-78717>

⁶Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. 913-XII dated 02.09.1993, <https://lex.uz/docs/-112170>

⁷Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. PF-5847 dated 08.10.2019, <https://lex.uz/docs/-4545884>

Prosecutors should also pay attention to issues of bilateral legal regulation of the same type of social relations at the level of settlements and urban districts. These shortcomings lead to conflicts not only in the activities of local government bodies, including the use of the city budget.

District and city prosecutors must ensure the timely adoption of municipal regulations and amendments in the field of patriotic education through the prosecutor's response measures.

Because, Article 15 of the Law "On General Military Obligation and Military Service" assigns responsibility to the executive authorities of the Republic of Uzbekistan to carry out work on patriotic education, and then to adopt patriotic education programs at the citizen level. need

At the same time, in connection with the improvement of the regulatory framework for patriotic education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, including those related to the adoption of legal documents at the republican level, prosecutors pay attention to the legality of current regional regulatory legal documents. should focus. accepts documents and tries to bring them into line with the requirements of the current legislation.

The analysis of the practice of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of the laws on patriotic education allows us to conclude that improper fulfillment or even non-fulfillment of the duty assigned to one on patriotic education leads to the commission of offenses and crimes by persons living in this area. . specific area. The lack of effective organization of the system of patriotic education in the region leads to an increase in crime and a low level of moral development.

Unfortunately, today there are municipalities in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan that have not set the appropriate direction in their municipal programs.

Prosecutors are advised to create interactive maps that highlight areas where patriotic education is not being carried out or is not adequately organized, depending on the severity of the offenses and crimes committed. Identifying places where crimes and offenses were committed.

This technology was proposed and is being developed by the Department of Statistics of the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Analyzing the obtained maps, it is possible to draw a conclusion about inefficient areas of local state authorities, educational authorities, guardianship and guardianship authorities, internal affairs authorities, etc.

assigned to the prosecutors is related to the organization of the fight against the internal threat of undermining the historical, spiritual and patriotic traditions in the field of protection of the Motherland through the influence of information on young citizens, as defined in the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan . ⁸In order to improve military-patriotic education and increase its efficiency, important directions of action for unifying the efforts of society and the state have been defined.

We believe that the above tasks of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of laws on patriotic education should be strengthened in a special order of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at strengthening this area of prosecutor's control.

⁸Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, O'RQ-458 dated 09.01.2018, <https://lex.uz/docs/-3495885>

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prosecutor's Office" gives the General Prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan the right to issue orders and instructions regulating the organization of the system of the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Both are important legal documents for the organization of the prosecutor's supervision. In conclusion, it can be said that today, taking into account the proven relevance of the prosecutor's control over the implementation of laws on educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, in order to increase the effectiveness of the prosecutor's control in this field, the prosecutor's control should be clearly defined in the relevant regulatory documents.

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